

ПЕДАГОГИКА ВА ПСИХОЛОГИЯДА ИННОВАЦИЯЛАР

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THE PROBLEM OF INTERACTION BETWEEN EDUCATION AND DEVELOPMENT

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ANNOTATION

In the article, the problem of interaction between education and training in the management of human personality based on modern psychology is discussed. The correlation between education and upbringing is very important in personality development, and the levels of mental and physiological development are considered as a necessary tool. At the same time, the role of education in personality development is considered in examples and filled with the opinions of foreign researchers.

Key words: education, communication, opportunities, interaction

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ПРОБЛЕМА ВЗАИМОДЕЙСТВИЯ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ И РАЗВИТИЯ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье обсуждается проблема взаимодействия образования и обучения управлению личностью человека на основе современной психологии. Соотношение образования и воспитания очень важно в развитии личности, а уровни психического и физиологического развития рассматриваются как необходимый инструмент. При этом роль образования в развитии личности рассмотрена на примерах и наполнена мнениями зарубежных исследователей.

Ключевые слова: образование, общение, возможности, взаимодействие.

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TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISHNING O'ZARO TA'SIRIDAGI MUAMMOLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada zamonaviy psixologiya ta'limoti asosida inson shaxsini shakllantirishda ta'lim va tarbiya va rivojlanishning o'zaro ta'siri muammosi keng doirada muhokama qilingan. Shaxs rivojlanishida ta'lim va tarbiyaning o'zaro mutanosibliги o'ta ahamiyatli bo'lib, aqliy va fiziologik rivojlanishning darajalari zaruriy vosita sifatida ko'rib chiqiladi. Shu bilan birga, shaxs rivojlanishida ta'limning o'rni misollarda ko'rib chiqiladi va chet el tadqiqotchilari fikrlari bilan to'ldiriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: ta'lim, rivojlanish, imkoniyat, o'zaro aloqa

The problem of interaction between education and training and development in the formation of human personality based on the modern teaching of psychology is becoming a topic of discussion in a wide range. Development usually means both types of events and these concepts are closely related:

1) biological, organic development of the brain, development in terms of its anatomical-physiological structure;

2) mental development as certain growth levels of mental development, as specific mental maturity. It is self-evident that mental development is related to the biological structure of the brain and this feature must be taken into account in educational work, because education cannot deny that the brain is organically formed.

However, it cannot be said that the organic formation of the brain structure takes place on the basis of its strict biological laws without being completely connected to the environment and education. Environment, education, and appropriate exercise help the brain structure organically. What is the role of education in this process? Does education lead development or vice versa? The solution of this problem determines the content and methodology of the educational process, the content of educational programs and textbooks.

In this regard, the German psychologist V. Stern put forward the idea that education follows mental development and adapts to it. Contrary to this opinion, the Russian psychologist L.S. Vygotsky was the first to put forward the rule that education and upbringing have a leading role in the child's mental development, and clearly expresses it that education precedes development and follows it behind. According to the first point stated above, education uses only what is achieved by development.

Therefore, the process of mental maturation should not be interfered with and should not be interfered with. It is necessary to bear passively with patience until the opportunity for education is given.

The theory of the Swiss psychologist J. Piaget is based on the same ideas. According to J. Piaget, the child's mental growth develops on the basis of its own internal laws and goes through a series of qualitatively unique genetic stages. Education can only speed up or slow down the process of mental maturation, but it cannot have any significant effect on the process of mental maturation. Therefore, education must obey the laws of development. For example, it is useless to teach a child to think logically without being able to think logically. It follows from this that the different stages of education are dependent on the specific age at which the child's psychological capabilities are matured.

It is worth noting that education plays a leading role, and education and development are interdependent; they are not two separate processes, but one whole process. There can be no full mental development without education. Education drives development, development follows. When the necessary conditions arise, education develops the skills of logical thinking and becomes the basis for appropriate intellectual development. However, education, while stimulating development, relies on development itself, takes into account the characteristics of the achieved level of development, internal rules of development. Although the possibilities of education are very wide, they are not unlimited. The great Russian psychologist L.S. Vygotsky approaches the problem of education and development from the point of view of socio-historical process and states that the acquisition of knowledge is the process of participation in the culture created in the historical development of mankind.

According to the cultural-historical theory of the development of mental functions, which he advanced, the development of mental activity is considered to acquire a "cultural" form, assuming its external and then internal expression with various symptoms, while directly re-examining its "natural" form. In this regard, L.S. Vygotsky's concept of "the closest zone of mental development" introduced into psychology is of great importance. The real essence of this is that the child's independent activity is carried out in cooperation with adults, under his guidance. The concept of "the closest zone of mental development" introduced by L.S. Vygotsky provides an opportunity to understand the obvious content of the general rule that "education precedes development." Despite the explanation of E. Thorndike and J. Piaget that education and development are the same thing, L. S. Vygotsky states: "Child development can never be considered as a shadow outside the education of the educational institution." In addition, he strongly criticizes psychologists who believe that education and development are independent processes. P.P. Blonsky attaches great importance to the role of education in child development. Therefore, it is emphasized that the mental development of students is directly related to the content of the educational program. According to him, in the process of education, children get used to act on the basis of a certain rule.

As a result of the educational effect, students have control over themselves and their mental activity. Psychologist-scientists V. V. Davidov, P. Ya. Galüperin, D. B. Elyukonin, N. A. Menchinskaya, A. A. Lyublinskaya, E. G. Goziev emphasize the leading role of education in development in their research. Even if the factors and conditions of mental development are determined, it is natural to ask what are the sources of changes in the psyche, what are the forces that drive mental development. The forces driving a child's mental development are complex and diverse.

The essence of development consists of the struggle of contradictions, internal conflicts, the forces that directly drive the child's mental development, the contradictions between the old and the new that arise and are eliminated in the process of education and upbringing.

Such conflicts include, for example, conflicts between the new needs arising from the activity and the possibilities of their satisfaction; conflicts between the growing physical and mental capabilities of the child and the old, structured forms of interaction and types of activities; conflicts between the current level of psychic development and the day-by-day increasing demands of society, community, and adults. For example, there is a conflict between readiness for independent volitional activity in a student at the age of a small educational institution and the dependence of actions on the existing situation or direct inner experiences.

In teenagers, the strongest conflicts are between, on the one hand, his self-evaluation and the level of his own demands, and on the other hand, his inner experience of the attitude of others towards him, as well as his inner experience of his real position in the community; it arises between the need to participate as a full-fledged member in the life of adults and the incompatibility of their own opportunities for this.

All the indicated contradictions are resolved by the formation of psychic activities of a somewhat higher level. As a result, the child rises to a higher stage of mental development. The need is satisfied - the conflict disappears. But a satisfied need creates a new need. This conflict is replaced by another conflict, progress continues.

Development does not consist only of the process of pure quantitative changes, i.e. the increase or decrease of some mental phenomena, properties and qualities, but it is related to the appearance of qualitatively new properties, i.e. newly created qualities. Psychologists note that there are general laws of mental development. However, these laws are secondary to the influence of the environment, because the specific characteristics of these laws depend on the conditions of life, activities and upbringing. Such general patterns include, first of all, the unevenness of mental development. The essence of this is that in any conditions, even in the most favorable conditions of education and upbringing, various mental signs, functions and characteristics of a person do not stop at one level of development.

In certain young periods of the child, there are extremely favorable conditions for development in one or another direction of the psyche and some of these conditions are of a temporary, transitory nature. Such age periods, which are the most favorable conditions for the

development of one or another mental characteristics and qualities, are called sensitive periods. (L.S. Vygotsky, A.N. Leontev). The existence of such a period of sensitivity is caused by the pattern of organic maturation of the brain, certain mental processes and characteristics and life experience.

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